

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D8.3

Report of impact and key results

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1. Executive Summary

The aim of the CINECA project is to create a federated cloud enabled infrastructure to make population scale genomic and biomolecular data accessible across national cohorts in Europe, Canada and Africa, and to support federated data analysis in the same cohorts. As a result of the work done in the project, CINECA has produced multiple outputs like standards, resources, APIs, tools, and training. In this report we will present the sustainability plans for the project key outputs to ensure the work done in the CINECA project is maintained in the long-term and can be used by the scientific community after the CINECA project's ending.

This deliverable will focus solely on the CINECA output's sustainability. A more detailed description of the project's achievements and impact are described in Deliverable D8.4 Report of main achievements, impacts, sustainability and exploitation¹.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached the following objectives:

- a) To provide insights on the sustainability plan for the different CINECA outputs to assure they will be available to the scientific community after the end of the CINECA project.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

In the last 40 years the field of disease research has witnessed a dramatic surge in the number of cohort datasets. These datasets, initially established for studying specific diseases, have now become invaluable resources that can be repurposed to further our understanding of various health conditions. However, accessing and utilizing this data comes with significant challenges due to its sensitive nature and diverse storage locations across different countries and continents.

CINECA project has worked on overcoming these obstacles by focusing on the 'Researcher Journey' (Figure 1), the different steps a clinician/researcher would follow in order to re-use this data:

Figure 1. Summary of steps a researcher/clinician needs to take to find, access and analyze federated data, complying always with the corresponding ELSI framework².

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/8099739>

² Icons from <https://www.flaticon.com/>

Federated data discovery

Cohort datasets are dispersed across various locations, encompassing different countries and continents. These datasets are stored in diverse research institutions, hospitals, government agencies, etc. The clinician/researcher interested in a particular type of data needs tools to “discover” where the data they need to perform their studies is located.

Data access

Once the clinician/researcher has identified the data they are interested in, they need to be provided access to it. Data Access Committees (DACs) are used to grant access on a project basis, but with the growing number of data sources dispersed across multiple locations there is a need for a federated approach, which will support automation of the data access process.

Data harmonization

The clinician/researcher accessing cohort datasets from different sources seeks to combine them to increase sample size and statistical power, which will enable more robust analyses. Harmonization ensures that variables and measurements align across locations, facilitating the consistent merging of data.

Federated data analysis and healthcare applications

The clinician/researcher aims to analyze the data obtained from the different accessed cohorts, but the traditional method of accessing and analyzing these datasets individually is no longer feasible due to the scale of data, increased security requirements, and jurisdictional restrictions on data export. Therefore, an alternative approach involving federated analysis, where the analysis is performed on the data itself through standardized interfaces, while preserving privacy, needs to be implemented. In addition, tools need to be provided so that federated healthcare applications can assist clinicians in their diagnosis.

Trans-national harmonised ELSI framework

Privacy concerns, informed consent, data sharing agreements, and regulatory compliance are critical considerations when accessing and sharing cohort datasets. Therefore, all the processes in the ‘Researcher Journey’ need to consider ethical, legal, and social implications (ELSI), while complying with national and international regulations.

The CINECA project has focused its work in developing different tools to overcome the issues encompassing the ‘Researcher Journey’. In this report we summarize the sustainability plans for these tools so that they can be used after the completion of the project.

3.2 Description of Work

Here we summarise the outputs developed in the CINECA project in each step of the ‘Researcher Journey’, and explain the sustainability strategy applied for them.

Federated data discovery

Beacon v2 API

A Beacon API is a genomics discovery tool that allows the search of genomic variants and associated information without jeopardising the privacy of the dataset, and it does it by aggregating worldwide genomics dataset through a shared query protocol³. CINECA has deployed 3 Beacon endpoints⁴ during the project; one at the European Genome-Phenome Archive⁵ (EGA) in UK, one at the Center for Scientific Computing⁶ (CSC) in Finland, and one at the Canadian Centre for Computational Genomics⁷ (C3G) in Canada. A 4th beacon for H3Africa is underway in being deployed at the University of Cape Town⁸ (UCT) in South Africa.

Sustainability: Using a GA4GH-approved standard like Beacon v2⁹ ensures that this tool will be maintained after the end of the CINECA project and in the long-term. Therefore, the cohorts involved in the CINECA project not only will be able to keep using Beacon v2 after the end of the project for clinicians/researchers to discover their cohorts, but will be able to implement new Beacon improvements in further versions of the tool that will be developed in the future.

Federated Discovery Portal

CINECA developed a Query Expansion Service¹⁰ to improve findability and searchability of distributed cohort data, where search terms are expanded to similar concepts in other ontologies for the local Beacon endpoints. In addition, CINECA created a Discovery Portal¹¹ for users to easily query the CINECA cohorts with a user-friendly interface. This Portal has incorporated the Query Expansion tools previously described.

Sustainability: The Portal¹², network and services will be maintained by the CRG, and hosted at the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre, with whom the EGA has an agreement for permanent archiving of data and hosting of services.

³ <https://beacon-project.io/>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/8093973>

⁵ <https://ega-archive.org/test-beacon-apis/cineca>

⁶ <https://b1mg-beacon.rahtiapp.fi/api>

⁷ <https://bqc19.c3g.calculquebec.ca/api/beacon/>

⁸ https://beacon.h3abionet.org/h3a_wgs/info

⁹ https://www.ga4gh.org/news_item/new-release-of-ga4gh-beacon-expands-genomic-and-clinical-data-access/

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/record/4609335>

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/8099693>

¹² <https://beacon-network-cineca-demo.ega-archive.org/>

Data access

GA4GH Passports and AAI infrastructure

CINECA has contributed to the development of GA4GH standards involved in providing data authorization and authentication for users in federated infrastructures, the GA4GH Passports and AAI standards, and in the transition from ELIXIR AAI to Lifescience AAI. In addition, CINECA has implemented these standards for a proof-of-concept cross-authentication and authorization between infrastructures located in Europe (UK) and Canada (CanDIG).

Sustainability: The employment of GA4GH standards, like GA4GH Passports and AAI, ensures sustained support from the research community. In addition, the methods used in the CINECA project to connect infrastructures located in different jurisdictions can be reused by other projects, which will expand their

Data harmonization

Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology

In order to support data discovery across jurisdictions, it's necessary for cohorts to be able to harmonize their participants' data. The GECKO¹³ (Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology) is a semantic platform developed by CINECA, based on the CINECA Metadata Model¹⁴, that enables cohort owners to easily harmonize their data.

Sustainability: Besides being published as a deliverable, the GECKO is a resource publicly available through the EBI Ontology Search¹⁵ (OLS) website. Therefore, any person can use the same ontology structure for harmonizing their cohorts. In addition, GECKO has been used in the International HundredK+ Cohort Consortium (IHCC) to harmonize cohorts' data dictionaries, which are discoverable through the IHCC Atlas¹⁶. The fact that GECKO is already being employed in an International project like IHCC ensures this system will be used beyond the duration of the CINECA project.

DUO codes

CINECA has been involved in the development of the Data Use Ontology¹⁷ (DUO) codes, a machine-readable file used to provide data use categories to datasets, which eases Data Access Committee's burden of evaluating data access requests manually.

Sustainability: DUO codes are a GA4GH approved standard¹⁸, which assures its wide adoption, and future maintenance.

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/record/5055308>

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/4575460>

¹⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies>

¹⁶ <https://atlas.ihccglobal.org/>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

¹⁸ https://www.ga4gh.org/news_item/data-use-ontology-approved-as-a-ga4gh-technical-standard/

Synthetic Datasets

At the beginning of the CINECA project developers faced the challenge of requiring data access to human cohort data to develop their tools, which is a time-consuming process. To overcome this problem CINECA developed 4 Synthetic Cohort Datasets¹⁹, which are based on actual CINECA cohorts but don't contain any sensitive data. Using these datasets allowed developers to create new tools while eliminating the risk of compromising individual privacy.

Sustainability: All 4 CINECA Synthetic Cohort Datasets are publicly available, and will be after CINECA project's end, either at EGA (Synthetic Cohort Europe UK1²⁰) or at Zenodo (Synthetic Cohort Europe CH SIB²¹, Synthetic Cohort Africa H3ABionet²², Synthetic Cohort NA Canada CHILD²³). Therefore, any other project requiring Synthetic Cohort Datasets in their studies can either directly use the CINECA datasets, or create their own Synthetic Datasets by following CINECA's Synthetic Cohort creation documentation.

Federated data analysis

eQTL analysis workflows

The CINECA project has created multiple workflows to perform federated genetic analysis of molecular traits across multiple international cohorts. In particular, a use case was created to study expression Quantitative Trait Loci²⁴ (eQTL).

All the eQTL workflows are written with NextFlow language, have all software dependencies packed with Singularity/Docker containers available from quay.io²⁵ and come with small test datasets. In addition, these workflows are modular, which allows for different workflows to be combined and achieve different data analysis objectives, and they are containerized, which facilitates their implementation in different types of infrastructures.

Sustainability: CINECA eQTL workflows have been developed to facilitate their accessibility and usability by the research community. All workflows are publicly available in Github²⁶ with descriptions of how they were created and how to use them. In addition, their modularity provides flexibility, allowing users to combine and adapt them to their specific research purposes. Moreover, they can be easily implemented in different organizations' compute infrastructures due to their containerized system. All these characteristics will facilitate workflow's adoption by users and projects outside and beyond CINECA.

¹⁹ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/cineca-synthetic-datasets>

²⁰ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001006673>

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/5082689>

²² <https://zenodo.org/record/4955933>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/record/5122832>

²⁴ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/biochemistry-genetics-and-molecular-biology/expression-quantitative-trait-loci>

²⁵ <https://quay.io/>

²⁶ <https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue>

Federated healthcare applications

Federated Biomarker Discovery service

CINECA has developed a service to evaluate genomic and transcriptomic features as biomarkers of disease progression and patient stratification²⁷. This service uses Galaxy²⁸, a FAIR and user-friendly web-based platform designed for biomedical research, which provides a wide range of tools and workflows for various analysis tasks, including genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and more. A CINECA use case was developed to perform a trio analysis²⁹ to find the causative variant in an autosomal dominant inherited disease.

Sustainability: The CINECA workflow for trio analysis is publicly available in the Galaxy platform. Galaxy enables researchers to perform complex analyses without requiring extensive programming skills, which will facilitate CINECA workflow's adoption by other users or projects. In addition, the workflow included GA4GH standards and open-source tools like HTSget³⁰, PyEGA3³¹ or Beacon³² for data access and retrieval. Adopting GA4GH standards together with implementing the workflow in the Galaxy platform assures all the components will be maintained and accessible beyond the end of the CINECA project.

FAIR Compliant Diagnostic Services

Analyzing complex sequencing data can require high computational power usually not accessible to researchers or clinicians. To overcome this issue, CINECA developed a Variant Interpretation Pipeline (VIP) to identify pathological variants utilizing a high-performance computing (HPC) system, which enables researchers to leverage powerful computing resources remotely, allowing them to perform resource-intensive analyses on their own computers. Then, this workflow was used to perform a Diagnostic Reporting Application, a FAIR-compliant reporting demonstrator designed to generate diagnostic reports based on genomic SNP variants³³.

Sustainability: CINECA has used an HPC located and maintained by the UMCG³⁴, which is being used also in other projects like EJP-RD³⁵ or Solve-RD³⁶. The VIP is publicly available³⁷, and thanks to the flexibility of using HPC it can be re-used by multiple organizations independent of their computing infrastructure. The Diagnostic Reporting Application uses the VIP with Disgenet³⁸, an open platform that provides information to generate a diagnostic report for clinicians. In addition, the whole workflow uses Molgenis EMX2, a platform that complies with the FAIR principles.

²⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/7925781>

²⁸ <https://usegalaxy.org/>

²⁹

<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/variant-analysis/tutorials/trio-analysis/tutorial.html>

³⁰ <https://academic.oup.com/bioinformatics/article/35/1/119/5040320>

³¹ <https://ega-archive.org/download/downloader-quickguide-APIv3>

³² <https://beacon-project.io/>

³³ <https://zenodo.org/record/7925804>

³⁴ <https://umcgresearch.org/w/high-performance-computing>

³⁵ <https://www.ejprarediseases.org/>

³⁶ <https://solve-rd.eu/>

³⁷ <https://github.com/molgenis/vip>

³⁸ <https://www.disgenet.org/>

Curation-support application for care planning

A CINECA workflow³⁹ has been developed to assist clinicians in assessing genetic variants' pathogenicity, and generating recommendations for potential treatments.

Sustainability: This workflow makes use of Variomes API⁴⁰, a variant search engine developed and maintained by the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics⁴¹ (SIB) to assess variants' pathogenicity. Treatment recommendation data is obtained from ATC⁴² and Drugbank⁴³ public databases. Finally, a demonstrator⁴⁴ was created which will be maintained also by SIB.

Dissemination and communication

The CINECA project has been focused on disseminating the project's achievements to the scientific community. In total, 59 learning interventions have been delivered, including staff visits, webinars, workshops and training events, short training videos, and a Learning Pathway.

Sustainability: All CINECA learning interventions are publicly accessible through the CINECA website⁴⁵, which holds all the project's relevant information. This website will be maintained by EBI for at least 5 years. In addition, all the videos released are available through the CINECA Youtube website⁴⁶, which assures they will be accessible in the long term. Finally, the Learning Pathway⁴⁷ is a resource hosted in the Training⁴⁸ site at EMBL-EBI, which also secures its availability after the end of the CINECA project.

ELSI framework

CINECA has documented the Legal and Ethical issues the CINECA project faced⁴⁹, provided insights of the ELSI frameworks in Canada, Europe and Africa⁵⁰, and provided recommendations⁵¹ to assure a safe and compliant data sharing between the cohorts involved in the CINECA project. In addition, multiple ELSI trainings and webinars were performed throughout the project.

Sustainability: All the ELSI documentation is publicly available, and can provide insights to other international projects aiming to develop infrastructures to share sensitive data among different jurisdictions. In addition, all training and webinars are available at the CINECA Youtube channel, which will assure their accessibility in the long term.

³⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7925825>

⁴⁰ <https://variomes.text-analytics.ch/>

⁴¹ <https://www.sib.swiss/>

⁴² https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-211-89836-9_64

⁴³ <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/46/D1/D1074/4602867>

⁴⁴ <https://denver.hesge.ch/cineca/demo/step6>

⁴⁵ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/@cinecaproject1265>

⁴⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/materials/cineca-federated-data-analysis/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/>

⁴⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/3943732>

⁵⁰ <https://zenodo.org/record/4298450>

⁵¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7267158>

3.3 Next steps

The goal of the CINECA project is to create a federated cloud-based infrastructure that allows researchers and clinicians to easily access and analyze cohort data from different locations. To achieve this, we examined the challenges and obstacles faced at each step of the Researcher Journey and focused on finding solutions to overcome them. Our aim has been to improve the current state of the art techniques for data access and analysis from multiple sources and make it more accessible to the scientific community.

Sustainability strategy has always been a major concern in the CINECA project. To develop the right tools to achieve CINECA's goals is as important as having the correct strategies implemented to assure their sustainability after the project ends. Therefore, sustainability has always been embedded in the products CINECA has developed, with different strategies being used: developing and using standards (e.g. those approved by the GA4GH), which assures a wide adoption by the scientific community, and future compatibility with developments created from other projects; using open-source tools (e.g. Galaxy platform or Github repository) which allows researchers/clinicians to freely access and implement the technologies developed; use of existing infrastructures for the implementation of the project outputs, which will guarantee their sustainability through those projects (e.g. EGA or LS AAI); use of cross-project developments which expands both developments' availability and wide implementation (e.g. CINECA GECKO being used in the IHCC project).

In addition, all CINECA outputs (tools, infrastructures, workflows, training, documentation, etc) are open and available through multiple platforms (like Zenodo, Github, Youtube, and others). Therefore, other projects working in the same field will have full access to the work done in the CINECA project, and we hope the work done in CINECA serves as a model for future projects, which will help expand on what has been already done to accomplish the objective of creating a reliable, easy-to-use and secure federated cloud-enabled infrastructure.

4. Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AAI	Authorization & Authentication Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
C3G	Canadian Centre for Computational Genomics
CSC	Center for Scientific Computing
DAC	Data Access Committee
DUO	Data Use Ontology
EGA	European Genome-Phenome Archive
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Implications
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GECKO	Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology
H3Africa	Human Heredity & Health in Africa
HPC	High Performance Computing
IHCC	International HundredK+ Cohort Consortium
OLS	Ontology Search
QTL	Quantitative Trait Loci
UCT	University of Cape Town
UMCG	University Medical Center Groningen
WP	Work Package

5. Delivery and schedule

On time delivery

6. Adjustments made

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7. Appendices

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